

ISic0182

I.Sicily inscription 0182

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Found in excavations in the house of Sig. De Michele, barone di S. Giuseppe, Termini Imerese, 1877

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 19.5 cm

Width 34 cm

Depth 7.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Herennia

2. C(ai) f(ilia) Polla

3. have

Apparatus

Text from ILTermini

Translation (en)

Herennia Polla, daughter of Gaius. Farewell!

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285226

EDR 127390

EDCS 22100113

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7411 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 104
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Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 227

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